

BIO-EFFICACY OF SOME INSECTICIDES AND BOTANICALS AGAINST MUSTARD APHID, *LIPAPHIS ERYSIMI* KALT. (HEMIPTERA : APHIDIDAE) ON INDIAN MUSTARD

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ABSTRACT : To evaluate the bio-efficacy and economics of some insecticides and botanicals against mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* Kalt. on Indian mustard under field conditions. The treatment of imidacloprid 0.005% was found most effective followed by thiamethoxam 0.005% and dimethoate 0.03% which reduce up to 95.54, 91.80 and 90.85 per cent of aphid during both the years. The treatments of acephate 0.02%, profenophos 0.03% and spinosad 0.01% were existed moderately effective group in reducing aphid population. The treatment of karanj oil 5ml/litre, NSKE 5ml/litre and Neem oil (1ml/litre) were observed to be less effective which reduce up to 53.65, 58.41 and 59.93 per cent aphid population during both years.. The maximum seed yield of 1866 kg/ha was recorded in imidacloprid, which at par with thiamethoxam (1813 kg/ha) and dimethoate (1757 kg/ha). The lowest seed yield was obtained from untreated plots (1239 kg/ha).

Key words : Imidacloprid, Indian mustard, mustard aphid, thiamethoxam, dimethoate.

INTRODUCTION

Oilseeds have been the backbone of agricultural economy of India since long. Indian vegetable oil economy is the fourth largest in the world next to U.S.A., China and Brazil. Oilseed brassicas because of resilience to grow under diverse agroclimatic conditions have gained good momentum in India. These crops are second most important after groundnut in our country contributing about 22.6% of the total oil production (Anonymous, 2013). India accounts for 14.8% of rapeseed production at global level and occupies prime position in the world (Singh, 2014). Indian mustard [*Brassica juncea* (L.) Czern and Coss.] is the premier oilseed brassica which covers about 85-90% of the total area under cultivation of all these crops. During past few years, it has gained substantial importance due to the fact that it possesses inherent high yielding ability and relative tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses with wider adaptation. At national level it is grown over an area of 6.45 million ha with production and productivity of 7.28 million tons and 1128 kg/ha, respectively (Anonymous, 2015). Rajasthan ranks first in both area (29.27 lakh ha) and production (37.64 lakh t) with productivity of 1286 kg per ha in Rajasthan (Anonymous, 2014). Mustard (*Brassica juncea* (L.) Czern and Coss), is an important oilseed crop is damaged by a number of insect-pests. viz., sawfly (*Athalia*

lugens), aphid (*Lipaphis erysimi*), painted bug (*Bagrada hilaris* L.) and leaf miner (*Phytomyza horticola*). According to Sachan and Purwar (2007), rapeseed and mustard is attacked by more than 43 insect species, out of which mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) is the key pest of the crop in India. The most favorable temperature for *L. erysimi* is 20°C or below. Cloudy and cold weather help in accelerating the growth of insects. Among these, mustard aphid, *L. erysimi* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) is the major limiting factor causing up to 96 per cent yield losses and 5-6 per cent reduction in oil content (Shylesha *et al*, 2006). Singh *et al* (2012) reported 9 to 95 per cent reduction in yield at differed places in India. Both nymph and adult stages of this pest cause economic damage by sucking the cell sap from leaves, petioles, tender stems, inflorescence and pods. Due to continuous desapping by large aphid population yellowing, curling and subsequent drying of leaves take place, which ultimately leads to formation of weak pods and undersized seeds in the pods. The aphids also secrete honeydew which provides suitable medium for the development of sooty mould which ultimately hampers the process of photosynthesis. A number of chemical insecticides have been found effective against this pest in different parts of the country (Singh and Verma, 2008; Singh and Singh, 2009). But the indiscriminate use of the insecticides has resulted into several problems like

environmental pollution, health hazards to human beings, toxicity to pollinators & natural enemies etc. (Singh, 2001) but the insecticides and botanicals using control of mustard aphid is a part of this work in order to work out to know effect of botanicals on aphid and effective management of this pest and avoiding harmful effect to the predators. New molecules are now emerging as available component of IPM strategies on all crops in view of their good efficacy to pest control and safety to non target organisms. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken to evaluate the bio-efficacy of the insecticides and botanicals against mustard aphid.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at Agronomy Farm of College of Agriculture, Department of Entomology, SKRAU, Bikaner during *Rabi* seasons of the year 2013-14 and 2014-15. It is located in north direction to Bikaner at 28.01°N latitude and 73.22°E longitude with an altitude of 234.70 meters above mean sea level. This region falls under agro-climatic zone I C (Hyper arid partially irrigated western plain zone) of Rajasthan and agro-climatic zone XIV (Western dry region) of India. For studying the effect of the insecticides and botanicals on mustard aphid, a field experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. Indian mustard variety 'Laxmi' was raised at spacing of 30 cm x 10 cm in plots of size 3 x 2.4m. Recommended agronomic practices except plant protection were followed for raising the crop. Six treatments of insecticides and three treatments of botanicals including control were T1: imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%, T2: thiamethoxam 25 WG @ 0.005%, T3: acephate 75 SP @ 0.02%, T4: profenophos 50 EC @ 0.03%, T5: spinosad 45 SC @ 0.01%, T6: dimethoate 30 EC @ 0.03%, T7: NSKE @ 5 ml/litre, T8: Karanj oil @ 5ml/litre and T9: Neem oil @ 1ml/litre and T10: control with no spray. The population of aphids was recorded on the ten randomly selected plants from each treatment one day prior to insecticide application and at 1, 3, 7 and 15 days after spray of insecticides. The aphids were counted from top 10 cm apical twigs of these selected plants with the help of a magnifying glass. The numbers of aphids per plant were converted into per cent reduction of aphid population over the control by Abbott formula. Yield was recorded from net plot area and converted into kilogram per ha and data were statistically analyzed as per statistical guidelines given by Gomez and Gomez (1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment revealed that the treatment of imidacloprid 0.005% was found most effective followed

by thiamethoxam 0.005% and dimethoate 0.03% during both the years. The treatments of acephate 0.02%, profenophos 0.03% and spinosad 0.01% were existed moderately effective group in reducing aphid population. The treatment of Neem oil (1ml/litre), NSKE (5ml/litre) and karanj oil (5ml/litre) were observed to be less effective during both the years. The aphids were not observed on the mustard crop up to last week of January and were observed initially during first week of February at flowering stage. Initial population of aphids was very low but increased gradually and reached to its peak (76.9 & 62.9 aphids/plant) during 9th and 8th SMW (4 & 3 week of February), respectively and then started declining gradually (Table 1). After spray, aphid population was significantly decreased in all the treated plots. The maximum reduction of aphid population was recorded in imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005% (81.07 aphids/10 cm twig) followed by thiamethoxam 25 WG @ 0.005% (79.77 aphids/10 cm twig), dimethoate 30 EC @ 0.03% (78.35 aphids/10 cm twig), these three treatments were statistically at par to each other (Table 2, Fig. 1). The treatments of acephate 0.02%, profenophos 0.03% and spinosad 0.01% with 68.33, 67.25 and 64.58 per cent reduction in aphid population and formed next best group of insecticides in their efficacy. The minimum reduction of aphid population (51.99%) was recorded in neem oil followed by NSKE (48.66%) and karanj oil (46.35%). However, these treatments were statistically at par and least effective in reduction of aphid population. Similar results were obtained 3, 7 and 15 days after treatment (Table 2). After 3rd day of application of insecticides, the maximum reduction of aphid population was recorded in the treatment of imidacloprid followed by thiamethoxam and dimethoate caused 95.54, 91.80 and 90.85 per cent respectively. However, these treatments were statistically at par to each other. The next effective treatments were acephate, profenophos and spinosad with 78.17, 76.17, and 73.53 per cent reduction in aphid population respectively. However, these were comparable to each other. The minimum reduction of aphid population (59.93%) was recorded in neem oil followed by NSKE (58.41%) and karanj oil (53.65%). However, these treatments were statistically at par to each other and observed least effective in reducing the aphid population. After 7th day of application of insecticides, the maximum reduction of aphid population was recorded in the treatment of imidacloprid followed by thiamethoxam and dimethoate resulted in 89.85, 87.76 and 86.94 per cent respectively. However, these treatments were statistically at par to each other. The treatments of acephate, profenophos and spinosad recorded 76.20, 74.33 and 67.74

Table 1 : Population of aphid per plant on mustard during *rabi*, 2013-14 & 2014-15.

S. No.	Standard Meteorological weeks	Aphid population / plant	
		2013-14	2014-15
1	6	9.4	12.8
2	7	16.2	24.7
3	8	35.5	62.9
4	9	76.9	47.8
5	10	29.7	29.2
6	11	12.3	12.6
7	12	4.6	3.9

However, these treatments were statistically at par to each-other. Yadav and Singh (2016) who reported maximum reduction of aphid by imidacloprid (91.84 %) followed by thiamethoxam (91.43%) and dimethoate (91.02%). Imidacloprid and thiamethoxam were found most effective against mustard aphid in field by Rohilla *et al* (2004). Prasad and Dey (2006) and Rathod *et al* (2003) found imidacloprid was significantly superior even after 14 days of treatment. Similarly Swarnalata *et al*. (2015) reported imidacloprid as most effective treatment followed by thiamethoxam, *Verticillium lecanii*,

Table 2 : Bio-efficacy of insecticides/botanicals against *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) on mustard during *rabi* 2013-14 & 2014-2015 (pooled).

Treatment	Concentration (%) & ml	Polled mean percent reduction of aphid on 10 cm terminal portion of central shoot/plant after spray				Yield (q./ha.)
		Spray Application				
		1 day *	3 days	7 days	15 days	
Imidacloprid	0.005	81.07(64.29)**	95.54(78.79)	89.85(73.12)	48.45(44.11)	18.66
Thiamethoxam	0.005	79.77(63.66)	91.80(75.95)	87.76(70.40)	47.34(43.47)	18.13
Acephate	0.02	68.33(55.79)	78.17(62.17)	76.20(60.79)	36.34(37.06)	16.45
Profenophos	0.03	67.25(55.14)	76.17(61.37)	74.33(59.62)	35.50(36.50)	16.28
Spinosad	0.01	64.58(53.51)	73.53(59.08)	67.74(55.49)	32.66(34.85)	15.97
Dimethoate	0.03	78.35(62.46)	90.85(74.04)	86.94(69.17)	44.97(42.11)	17.57
NSKE	5 ml/litre	48.66(44.23)	58.41(49.84)	48.71(44.21)	26.65(31.02)	14.90
Karanj oil	5ml/ litre	46.35(42.90)	53.65(47.08)	47.33(43.42)	24.05(29.35)	14.57
Neem oil	1ml/litre	51.99(46.14)	59.93(50.75)	53.27(46.86)	28.82(32.47)	15.00
Control		0.00(0.00)	0.00(0.00)	0.00(0.00)	0.00(0.00)	12.39
SEm±		1.79	2.51	2.20	1.18	0.61
CD (5%)		5.33	7.53	6.59	3.51	1.85
CV(%)		6.48	7.79	7.29	6.25	6.74

**Figures in parenthesis are Angular sin value

*Data based on three replications.

per cent reduction respectively and formed moderately group of insecticides. However, these treatments were comparable to each other. The minimum reduction of aphid population (53.27%) was recorded in Neem oil followed by NSKE (48.71%) and karanj oil (47.33%). However, these treatments were statistically at par to each-other and less effective in reducing the aphid population and after 15th day of application of insecticides, the maximum reduction of aphid population was recorded in the treatment of imidacloprid 0.005% followed by thiamethoxam 0.005% and dimethoate 0.03% with 48.45, 47.34 and 44.97 per cent, respectively. However, these treatments were statistically at par to each other. The treatments of acephate, profenophos and spinosad with 36.34, 35.50 and 32.66 per cent reduction in aphid population respectively and formed next best group of insecticides in their efficacy. However, these treatments were comparable to each other. The minimum reduction of aphid population (28.82%) was recorded in neem oil followed by NSKE (26.65%) and karanj oil (24.05%).

azadirachtin and dimethoate against cowpea aphid also support the present findings. Rohilla *et al* (2004) and Kantipudi *et al* (2013) recorded maximum control of mustard aphid with the application of thiamethoxam @100 g/ha followed by imidacloprid @ 150 ml/ha corroborate the present findings. Khedkar *et al* (2012) found imidacloprid 17.8 SL (0.008%), acetamiprid 20 SP (0.01%) and thiamethoxam 25 WG (0.0125%) as more effective treatment against *L. erysimi* partly support the present findings. Bhati and Sharma (2014) reported imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 20 g a.i./ha and clothianidine 50 WDP as moderately effective insecticides partly akin the present result. Yadav and Singh (2016) determined the bio efficacy of acephate insecticide and observed acephate as moderately effective treatment confirm the present findings, while Bhati & Sharma (2014) who reported acephate 75 SP @ 350 g. a.i./ha as most effective treatment against mustard aphid, partly corroborate the present result. Similarly, Parmar and Kapadia (2007) also found acephate and Imidacloprid as most effective

Fig. 1 : Bio-efficacy of insecticides/botanicals against *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) on mustard during rabi 2013-14 & 2014-15 (pooled).

treatment against mustard aphid that partly confirm the present findings. Kantipudi *et al* (2013) reported maximum control of mustard aphid with the application of thiamethoxam 25% WDG @100 g/ha followed by imidacloprid 17.8% SL @ 150 ml/ha. Kumar and Kumar (2016) reported dimethoate followed by malathion and neem oil (0.5%) as more effective insecticide for the control of *L. erysimi* Kalt. that partly akin the present result. Similarly, Tripathi *et al* (1988), Dubey *et al* (2001), Hazarika and Saharia (1981), Baral *et al* (1986) and Sinha *et al* (2001) who reported dimethoate as moderately toxic insecticide against *L. erysimi*, partly corroborate the present result. Gour and Pareek (2003), Arivudainambi and Prasad (2003) and Singh *et al* (2007) who observed NSKE and azadirachtin (Nimbecidine) as least effective insecticide in reducing the population of *L. erysimi* (Kalt.). Among the treatments, the maximum seed yield of 1866 kg/ha was recorded in imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%, which remained at par with thiamethoxam 25 WG @ 0.005% (1813 kg/ha) and dimethoate 30 EC @ 0.03% (1757 kg/ha). The seed yield from untreated plots was 1239 kg/ha (Table 2). Yadav and Singh 2016 reported maximum seed yield of 1630 kg/ha in imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 20 ga.i. per ha, which remained on par with thiamethoxam 25 WG @ 25 g a.i. per ha (1620 kg/ha) and dimethoate 30 EC @ 300 g a.i. per ha (1615 kg/ha). The seed yield from untreated plots was 1370kg/ha. Patel (2006) observed the highest seed yield in the plot treated with imidacloprid (1531 kg/ha) followed by thiamethoxam (1344) and acetamiprid (1225) akin with the present result. Bhati *et al* (2014) reported the maximum seed yield (15.56 q/ ha) in the treatment of Fipronil 5 SC @ 50 g. a.i./ha followed by Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 20 g. a.i./ha with yield (15.42 q/ha) also support the present result. Gour and Pareek (2003) reported maximum seed yield in plots treated with imidacloprid 0.05% (14.9 q/ha) followed by dimethoate 0.03% (11.9 q/ha) and acephate 0.05% (11.1 q/ha). Acephate, profenophos and spinosad which

provided yield of 16.45, 16.28 & 15.97 q ha⁻¹ respectively in the present investigation. Bhati *et al* (2014) who reported the higher seed yield in the plot treated with dimethoate 30EC @ 300 g a.i./ha followed acephate 75 SP @ 350 g a.i./ha with yield of 13.42 q /ha and 13.38 q /ha respectively. The lowest seed yield (14.57q /ha) was obtained from the plots treated with karanj oil followed by NSKE (14.90 q/ha) and neem oil (15.00 q/ha). Singh *et al* (2001) who obtained 12.28 q/ha seed yield in neem seed kernel extract (5%). The plot treated with imidacloprid resulted into the maximum mortality of mustard aphid with highest yield (1866 kg ha⁻¹). From the above discussion it may be concluded that among the tested insecticides, imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005% may be recommended for most economic and effective management of mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* on Indian mustard.

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